

The Effect of Badminton Racket String Tension on the Coefficient of Restitution of a Shuttlecock

Abstract

What is the relationship between the tension of a badminton racket (77.84 N – 100.93 N) and the coefficient of restitution from the bounce of the shuttlecock dropped from a height, while controlling the type of racket, shuttlecock, and string?

1. Introduction

As a kid, I spent hours watching my dad play badminton. He took the game seriously – he was always restringing his racket, sometimes even cutting the strings and starting over. I never really understood why, so one day, I asked him. He explained that different string tensions affect how the shuttlecock bounces off the racket, changing how much control or power a player has. At the time, it felt like just another one of those sports quirks, but as I started playing myself, I began to notice it too.

Badminton is one of the most widely played sports in the world, loved for its speed, skill, and accessibility. But beneath its fast rallies and sharp smashes lies a world of physics. When a shuttlecock collides with a racket, energy is transferred between the two objects. However, not all of this energy is returned to the shuttlecock – some is lost as heat, sound, or internal deformation of the racket strings. The coefficient of restitution (e) quantifies this energy retention after impact: a higher value of e indicates less energy loss and a more elastic collision. I observed that higher string tensions seemed to absorb more of the shuttlecock's energy, making my shots feel weaker despite my effort. This made me wonder, could string tension directly influence the coefficient of restitution?

To explore this, I decided to investigate how different string tensions affect the shuttlecock's rebound when dropped from a fixed height. By quantifying energy retention in these collisions, this study provides insight into the physics behind badminton performance and highlights the real-world applications of mechanical principles in sports.

2. Theoretical Framework and Hypothesis

The law of conservation of momentum states that during a collision within a closed system, in the absence of external forces, the total momentum of the system before and after the collision remains constant.

In an idealised, perfectly elastic collision – one where no energy is lost to air resistance, friction, or internal deformation – the coefficient of restitution (e) would be exactly 1, and the shuttlecock would rebound with the same speed at which it struck the racket.

In reality, air resistance, the coupling between the shuttlecock and the racket strings, and deformation of the shuttlecock all make the collision inelastic, so $e < 1$. Newton's law of restitution quantifies this energy loss as the ratio of the relative velocity of separation to the relative velocity of approach:

The coefficient is calculated using the formula:

$$e = \frac{v_{f1} - v_{f2}}{v_{i2} - v_{i1}}$$

where:

v_{f1} = velocity of the shuttlecock after collision

v_{f2} = velocity of the racket after collision

v_{i1} = velocity of the shuttlecock before collision

v_{i2} = velocity of the racket before collision

In this experiment, the racket remains stationary throughout, so $v_{i2} = v_{f2} = 0$, and the formula simplifies to:

$$e = \frac{v_{f1}}{-v_{i1}} \quad [1]$$

e lies between 0 (a perfectly inelastic collision, where all relative kinetic energy is lost) and 1 (a perfectly elastic collision, where none is lost).

Stiffer racket strings increase the effective stiffness of the string bed. A stiffer string bed is expected to deform less on impact, dissipating less energy to internal friction and heat, and returning more energy to the shuttlecock. Therefore, an increase in the coefficient of restitution with string tension is anticipated, corresponding to increased energy transfer and reduced losses.

3. Methodology

3.1 Variables

Independent Variable: String tension of the badminton racket

Values tested: 77.84 N, 80.72 N, 91.77 N, 96.04 N, 100.93 N

The values were chosen for a wide but realistic range of string tensions commonly used in amateur and professional badminton. The rackets were obtained from the school's sports department. String tensions were estimated using an online frequency-based calculator, which determines tension from the sound produced when striking the racket. While practical, this method introduces some uncertainty, as discussed in the weaknesses section.

Dependent Variable: The coefficient of restitution (e) based on the racket's string tension. The setup was recorded and analysed using Logger Pro™ to measure the shuttlecock's speed before and after hitting the racket (v_{f1} and v_{i1}). The coefficient of restitution was calculated using Equation [1].

Controlled Variables:

- **Type of Racket:** Five different rackets were used, each with varying string tensions. While the string tension differed between rackets, other factors such as frame stiffness, mass, and string bed area remained consistent. This ensured that the investigation focused solely on the effect of string tension on energy transfer and the coefficient of restitution (e). All rackets used were of the Fukang brand.
- **Shuttlecock:** The same Fukang shuttlecock was used throughout all trials to ensure consistency. Using different shuttlecocks could have introduced variations in mass, skirt material, and aerodynamic drag, which would have affected the bounce response and energy dissipation, ultimately impacting the calculation of the coefficient of restitution (e).
- **Drop Height:** Maintained at 1.5 metres using a fixed reference point on the whiteboard where the shuttlecock was dropped from, to ensure consistency. This height allows measurable rebound differences while minimising air resistance effects.
- **String Type – Durability string:** All rackets used the same string type and brand. The elastic properties and energy absorption rates of different strings vary, and differences of this kind can cause unpredictable rebound behaviour and bias results.
- **Contact Area on Racket:** The shuttlecock was always dropped by hand from a fixed position, using a reference line drawn on the whiteboard to ensure consistency. This helped align the drop position for each trial, minimising deviations in impact location and ensuring it consistently struck the racket's centre (also known as the 'sweet spot').

3.2 Apparatus

- 5 × Fukang badminton rackets with respective string tensions: 77.84 N, 80.72 N, 91.77 N, 96.04 N, 100.93 N
- 1 × shuttlecock (from an unopened pack)
- 2 × blocks with 20 cm height
- Logger Pro™ video analysis software
- 2 × metre rule (± 0.0005 m)
- 1 × roll of tape

3.3 Procedure

1. Set up the experiment as shown in Fig. 1, with the racket tension $T = 77.84$ N.
2. Drop the shuttlecock from a height of $h = 1.50$ m directly above the centre of the racket. Ensure no initial velocity or spin is imparted.

3. Record each drop and repeat it until 5 successful trials are collected where the shuttlecock lands close to the centre of the racket.
4. Repeat steps 1–3 for each of the remaining tensions.
5. Import each video into Logger Pro™.
6. Calibrate distance using the visible metre stick (1.5 m).
7. Use the software's video analysis tool to track the shuttlecock's vertical position frame-by-frame.
8. From the position-time data, Logger Pro automatically calculates velocity-time graphs.
9. Extract the initial velocity (just before impact) and the final velocity (just after rebound) from the graph.
10. For each tension value, compute the average velocities from the five trials.
11. Calculate the coefficient of restitution.
12. Record the calculated e values for each string tension and plot a graph of string tension vs coefficient of restitution.

Fig. 1: Experiment setup (Image captured using an iPhone 11)

Environmental Considerations: This experiment reused existing rackets from the school's sports department, avoiding the purchase of new equipment and following a zero-waste approach. No further ethical or environmental considerations apply.

4. Results

4.1 Raw Data

Table 1: Raw data table showing relationship between tension and initial/final shuttlecock velocity

Tension (N) (± 0.0981)	Initial (v_i) and final (v_f) velocities of the shuttlecocks (ms^{-1})									
	Trial 1		Trial 2		Trial 3		Trial 4		Trial 5	
	v_i	v_f	v_i	v_f	v_i	v_f	v_i	v_f	v_i	v_f
77.84N	-5.44	3.22	-5.38	3.18	-5.41	3.20	-5.47	3.23	-5.44	3.09
80.72N	-5.43	3.28	-5.40	3.25	-5.39	3.29	-5.52	3.28	-5.29	3.18
91.77N	-5.39	3.35	-5.41	3.32	-5.44	3.36	-5.49	3.34	-5.50	3.29
96.04N	-5.50	3.42	-5.43	3.39	-5.42	3.43	-5.64	3.43	-5.49	3.31
100.93N	-5.45	3.50	-5.42	3.45	-5.40	3.49	-5.47	3.41	-5.52	3.63

The initial velocities (v_i) of the shuttlecock are negative, and the final velocities (v_f) are positive in the table. This is because direction of motion is represented by sign convention:

- Negative is taken as the downward direction (when the shuttlecock is falling).
- Positive is taken as the upward direction (when the shuttlecock rebounds after hitting the racket).

For the sake of simplicity, the calculation of uncertainty in velocity disregards any effect caused by air resistance.

4.2 Data Processing

Example calculation for Average Coefficient of Restitution (e) and Standard Error:

(Note: All values used in the following calculations are taken from the first trial, where the racket tension is $T = 77.84$ N.)

Measured coefficient of restitution for Trial 1 using Equation [1]:

$$e = \frac{v_f}{|v_i|} = \frac{3.22}{| - (-5.44) |} = 0.59191$$

Calculate the average of the 5 trials:

$$\bar{e} = \frac{0.5919 + 0.5911 + 0.5915 + 0.5905 + 0.5680}{5} = \frac{2.9330}{5} = 0.5866$$

Calculate the Standard Deviation (SD):

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (e_i - \bar{e})^2}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{(0.5919 - 0.5866)^2 + \dots + (0.5905 - 0.5866)^2 + (0.5680 - 0.5866)^2}{4}}$$

$$= \sqrt{\frac{0.000110}{4}} = \sqrt{0.000110} = 0.0104$$

Calculate the Standard Error (SE):

$$SE = \frac{SD}{\sqrt{n}}$$

$$SE = \frac{0.0104}{\sqrt{5}} = \frac{0.0104}{2.236} = 0.00465$$

Table 2: Processed data table showing relationship between tension and average coefficient of restitution, along with standard error

Tension (N)	Average Coefficient of Restitution (e)	Standard Error
77.84	0.5866	0.00465
80.72	0.6023	0.00259
91.77	0.6117	0.00407
96.04	0.6180	0.00547
100.93	0.6412	0.00563

4.3 Uncertainty Analysis

To assess the reliability of the data, percentage uncertainty was calculated using the standard formula:

$$\text{Percentage uncertainty} = \left(\frac{\text{absolute uncertainty}}{\text{measured value}} \right) \times 100\%$$

For this research, the standard error in coefficient of restitution is taken as the absolute uncertainty, and the measured value is the average coefficient of restitution.

Sample calculation for Tension = 77.84 N:

$$\text{Percentage uncertainty} = \left(\frac{0.00465}{0.5866} \right) \times 100\% = 0.79\%$$

Table 3: Percentage Uncertainty

Tension (N)	Percentage Uncertainty (%)
77.84	0.79%
80.72	0.43%
91.77	0.67%
96.04	0.88%
100.93	0.88%

4.4 Graphical Uncertainty

Graph 1: Relationship between coefficient of restitution and tension with max (blue) and min (green) gradient lines shown

1. Calculating the graphical uncertainty in gradient

$$m\delta = \frac{\text{gradient}_{\max} - \text{gradient}_{\min}}{2(\text{predicted gradients})} = \frac{0.002809 - 0.001933}{2(0.001960)} = 0.2235 = 22.35\%$$

Hence, the graphical uncertainty in gradient is $\approx 22\%$.

This uncertainty represents the random error in the experiment due to the possible variation in the gradient based on the maximum and minimum best-fit lines. This can be considered an estimate of the total random uncertainty in the experiment.

2. Calculating the graphical uncertainty in the Y-intercept

$$Y_{\text{error}} = \frac{|\text{intercept}_{\max} - \text{intercept}_{\min}|}{2(\text{predicted intercept})} = 0.0881 \approx 8.81\%$$

The percentage uncertainty in the y-intercept, calculated from the spread between the maximum and minimum best-fit lines, is approximately 8.81%. The negative difference was ignored, as uncertainty represents the magnitude of variation.

Analysis and Conclusion

From the data presented, a clear relationship can be observed between the string tension of the badminton racket and the coefficient of restitution of the shuttlecock (Graph 1, above). The hypothesis proposed that an increase in string tension would result in a higher rebound, and this is supported by the processed data. The coefficient of restitution increased from 0.5866 at 77.84 N to 0.6412 at 100.93 N, demonstrating an overall trend of improved energy retention as string tension increased.

A strong linear correlation ($r = 0.9528$) exists between these variables, indicating that higher string tension leads to greater energy transfer efficiency. This supports the theoretical expectation that tightly strung strings deform less upon impact, allowing more energy to be returned to the shuttlecock, thereby increasing its rebound velocity. The data further reinforces the conclusion that string tension plays a dominant role in the energy retention of a collision.

The precision of the experiment is evident from the low standard errors, ranging from 0.00259 to 0.00563, and the percentage uncertainties, which remained under 1%, with the highest being 0.88%. This consistency across trials enhances the reliability of the observed trend. The results align well with the theoretical framework that increasing string tension reduces internal energy loss, leading to a more efficient energy transfer.

This conclusion is further supported by existing research – for instance, a finite-element study on the effect of string tension on the coefficient of restitution of a badminton racket string-bed also found a positive correlation between increased string tension and a higher coefficient of restitution. However, minor discrepancies between the experimental and literature values could be attributed to differences in experimental conditions, such as variations in racket type, shuttlecock material, and environmental factors.

Errors were most prominent at the extreme values of tension, particularly at 77.84 N and 100.93 N, where deviations from the trendline were larger. This could be due to the structural limitations of the racket at tensions beyond optimal levels. If a racket is too tightly strung, it becomes excessively stiff, which may reduce its ability to efficiently return energy, while under-tensioned strings may absorb too much energy, leading to a weaker rebound. This explains the slight variations seen in the experimental data.

In conclusion, the relationship between the tension of a badminton racket and the coefficient of restitution of a shuttlecock dropped from a height of 1.5 m is directly proportional. As string tension increases, the coefficient of restitution also increases, reinforcing the hypothesis that tighter strings enhance energy transfer efficiency in collisions.

Evaluation

Strengths

Strength	Explanation
Controlled variables	All variables aside from string tension were carefully controlled, including racket type, shuttlecock brand, drop height (1.5 m), and string type. This ensured that the changes observed in the coefficient of restitution were solely due to the changes in string tension.
Repeated trials	Each string tension level was tested with five trials. This reduced the effect of random errors and allowed for the calculation of mean values and standard error, improving the reliability and validity of the results.
Use of Logger Pro™ software	Logger Pro™ allowed frame-by-frame velocity tracking with calibrated distance, providing more accurate measurements of initial and final shuttlecock velocities. This increased the precision and consistency of the results.
Uncertainty consideration	Standard error and percentage uncertainty calculations ensured that the data was processed accurately and helped quantify the precision of the experiment.

Table 4: Strengths of the work

Weaknesses

Weakness	Explanation	Improvement
Inconsistent contact point on racket	Although efforts were made to drop the shuttlecock on the centre of the racket, slight deviations in contact point could lead to inconsistent rebounds and affect <i>e</i> .	Use a mechanical release system to ensure the shuttlecock is dropped in a controlled manner and strikes the same location on the string bed each time, at the same angle. Marking the ideal

Weakness	Explanation	Improvement
		impact point on the racket would also help ensure consistency.
Manual drop method	Dropping the shuttlecock by hand introduces human error, including inconsistent release height and angle, affecting initial velocity.	A fixed-height drop mechanism, such as a clamp or guided release tube, should be used to standardise the drop and minimise inconsistencies, ensuring uniformity in initial conditions across all trials.
Air resistance not accounted for	The experiment assumes negligible air resistance when calculating e , which may introduce slight inaccuracies, especially at lower velocities.	Conduct the experiment in a controlled indoor space with minimised airflow and include an air resistance analysis in the uncertainty discussion.
Trend line does not pass through all error bars	While the correlation between variables is high, the trend line does not pass through all error bars, suggesting potential systematic errors or inconsistencies in measurement. This could be due to variations in how the racket absorbed energy or slight misalignments in data collection.	Increasing the number of trials would improve the reliability of the trend and help smooth out inconsistencies. Conducting a residuals analysis would also allow for a more thorough evaluation of the data spread and model accuracy.
Unreliable string tension measurement	String tension was determined using an online website app rather than a direct measurement method. This could introduce inaccuracies, as the actual string tension may differ from the estimated values.	A string tension meter should be used to directly measure the string tension of each racket before conducting the experiment, removing reliance on external estimation methods.
Used rackets instead of new ones	The rackets used had been previously played with, meaning their string tension may have degraded over time. This could introduce variability in the results, as older strings might not behave the same way as freshly strung ones.	New or freshly strung rackets should be used to ensure that string tensions are accurate and consistent. All rackets should be restrung at the same time to control for differences in wear.

Table 5: Weaknesses and improvements

Extension

To build on this investigation, several modifications could be made to provide deeper insights into the factors affecting the coefficient of restitution (e). One extension could involve testing different types of shuttlecocks, specifically comparing plastic and feathered ones. Feathered shuttlecocks tend to deform more

on impact, potentially affecting energy transfer and leading to variations in e . Understanding how material properties influence rebound characteristics could offer a more complete picture of energy conservation in racket sports.

Another extension could involve expanding the range of string tensions beyond the current limits to determine whether the observed trend holds at extreme values. This could help identify whether there is a threshold at which the energy transfer efficiency significantly changes.

Additionally, incorporating high-speed video analysis would improve the accuracy of velocity measurements by providing precise frame-by-frame tracking of the shuttlecock's motion. This would reduce uncertainties associated with manual timing and allow for a more reliable calculation of e .

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